

TEACHING FUNNY WAYS OF ENGLISH TO SCHOOL STUDENTS

Khairyeva Ozoda Nuriddin kizi

7th school of Tashkent district

Abstract: *This article is about teaching the English language to schoolchildren. The phenomenon of bilingualism is mentioned as the main factor in teaching a foreign language in multi-national comprehensive schools in Uzbekistan. Methodical recommendations for overcoming these difficulties are also presented.*

Key words: *problem, sound, difference, verbal, visual, fluency, interference.*

In today's educational institutions, using advanced methods of teaching using modern pedagogical technologies, wide opportunities have been created for teaching foreign languages and training specialists who can speak these languages freely. The application of international standards in the teaching of foreign languages, modernization of teaching content, specific issues of using modern technologies in professional education, and the need to use advanced foreign experiences in the development of professional competences of the teacher have intensified. More and more people are speaking and understanding English in every corner of the world. English is also the number one language of communication. Therefore, teaching English to the young generation is very important in order to be among other countries during the period of rapid development of our country. Realizing this situation, our nation has recently developed a natural need to learn English.

In our country, J. Jalolov, G. Boqieva, T. Sattorov, G. T. Makhkamova, L. A. Akhmedova, U. Khoshimov, I. Yakubov, S. Musinov, L. Kirkham, M. T. Iriskulov, F. Rashidova studies Of course, everyone wants to learn this language easily and thoroughly through a modern teaching process that is convenient for them. But it is not always easy to achieve the expected result. When we use English as a communication tool, we should not create difficulties for the interlocutor, that is, we should use it efficiently and effectively to express our thoughts. Decision PQ-1875 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign

languages" set us the task of teaching foreign languages to the young generation by introducing advanced

methods of teaching using modern pedagogical and information communication technologies. . After this decision, the teaching of foreign language as a compulsory subject from the 1st grade was started in general education schools in Uzbekistan. This, in turn, required the search for ways to strengthen and optimize the educational process, update educational content and tools, increase motivation, and maintain interest during the educational process. When we observe the process of teaching a foreign language in secondary schools, we face several difficulties. We divided these challenges into external challenges and internal challenges.

External challenges can include:

1. Lack of sufficient methodological basis (general theoretical basis accepted in the educational system) of foreign language teaching in primary classes.
2. Lack of specialists teaching foreign languages to students of junior school age.

3. Lack of consistency in preschool and comprehensive school programs.

4. Financial costs for teaching a foreign language are high, and the effectiveness of language acquisition by students is low (they cannot fully use the language as a means of communication).

We can include the following in internal difficulties.

1. Lack of motivation to learn a foreign language among students of junior school age. One of the complicating reasons for the formation of such motivation is the stronger motivation of children towards their mother tongue. Because the child is just entering the world of his mother tongue, so this situation arouses more interest in the child. Also, the child learns the mother tongue in a natural environment. The surrounding world is directly related to this language. In a foreign language, an artificial environment is created for the child.

2. The problem of mastering a foreign language. In foreign language lessons, students involuntarily translate the language material into their native language, as a result of which the learning of foreign language units is carried out not with the help of the foreign language, but with the help of the native language. As a result, the mechanism of speech in a foreign language is replaced by the mechanism of the native language.

3. Personal psychological barrier, which is mainly the obstacle to the student being laughed at by other children for unusual sounds, pronunciation of words or mistakes in speech, shyness and similar situations. When working on listening comprehension during the teaching process, the presence of texts about daily news, life, culture, and history of the peoples of the country whose language is being studied increases the interest of the listeners.

When the teacher is teaching listening comprehension, that is, when the listener listens to the speech of an unfamiliar content, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

1. Understanding some words, sentences, sentences (fragmenting comprehension).
2. Comprehension in details.
3. Superficial understanding of the main arguments (overall comprehension).
4. Critical understanding (critical comprehension).

References:

1. Vereshchagina I.N., Rogova G.V. Methods of teaching English at the initial stage in educational institutions. - M.: "Enlightenment", 1998. -S. 43.
2. Galskova N.D., Nikitenko Z.N. Theory and practice of teaching foreign languages. - M.: "Iris-press", 2004. -S. 240.
3. Meshcheryakova V.N. I love English. Developing methods of teaching English. Tutorial. - M.: "Chistye Prudy", 2006. -S. 32.
4. Mitkina A.V. The impact of early learning a foreign language on the intellectual development of a child. - Collections of conferences of the Scientific Research Center Sociosphere: No. 39/2010. -FROM. 21–25.
5. Negnevitskaya E.I. Foreign language for the smallest: yesterday, today, tomorrow. / Journal "Foreign Languages at School", 1987, No. 6.
6. Udalova Yu.D. Experience in early learning of foreign languages in Russia and abroad. // Scientific community of students: interdisciplinary research: Sat. Art. by mat. IX Intern. stud. scientific-practical. conf. No. 6(9). URL: [https://sibac.info/archive/meghdis/6\(9\).pdf](https://sibac.info/archive/meghdis/6(9).pdf) (accessed 25.03.2018).
7. Musiol M., Villarroel M. My first English adventure. – London: «Pearson Education Limited», 2005.